

Effects of Investment and Labor on South East Sulawesi's Economic Growth

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
March 18, 2021

Accepted:
May 11, 2021

Keywords :

Investment, Labor,
Economic Growth,
ARDL model, ECM-
ARDL model

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4750361

Abstract

This article reports on the results of a study investigating the effect of investment and labor on South East Sulawesi Province's economic growth. The study used annual time series data on investment, labor, and gross regional domestic product of Southeast Sulawesi Province from 1999 to 2018. A distributed lag auto-regression (ARDL) model and an error correction model (ECM-ARDL) were used for the data analysis. The results show that in the short and long run, investment and labor affected economic growth.

Introduction

Economic growth is a macroeconomic indicator that is important for assessing the success of an economy, both state and regional. It shows the degree to which economic activity can produce extra income to enhance the well-being of society over a long term period. Sukirno (2008) said that industrial growth represents the region's economic development.

Kuznets (1955) argues that economic growth represents a rise in a country's long-term capacity to supply its population with different economic products. Such a rise is dictated by technological advancements and institutional and ideological adaptations to current demands. Further, Kuznets (1955) explained that economic growth is attributable to the combined effects of high productivity and a large population. Of these two factors, productivity growth is of paramount importance. This is in line with Adam Smith's statement that productivity growth leads to a rise in living standards. In the meantime, Kuznets (1955) emphasizes technological progress and innovation as a way to increase productivity growth in connection with the redistribution of labor from a less productive sector (i.e. agriculture) into a more productive one (i.e. manufacturing industry).

Investment represents a critical factor for accelerating a country's economic growth. The greater a country's investment, the higher its economic growth rate is. In line with this, the research results of Adhykary (2011) in Bangladesh provide empirical evidence that foreign investment had a positive and substantial effect on economic growth. Similarly, in his research, Athukorala (2003) also found that foreign investment positively impacted on Sri Lanka's economy. Likewise, Lipsey (2000) reported a positive effect on the host country due to international investment. A conflicting result, however, was documented by Rafiy et al. (2018) when examining the effect of investment on economic growth in Indonesia using net domestic investment data; investment did not influence economic growth.

With regard to research on the effect of labor on economic growth, several research studies have been conducted. Rustiono (2008) found that Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) growth in Central Java Province was positively influenced by labor, investment and local government spending. Surya (2008) also discovered that labor quality in the Western Sumatra Province had a major impact on economic growth.

The economic growth of South East Sulawesi showed some fluctuations between 2016 and 2018. By 2016, it stood at 6.51 and this figure increased marginally to 6.76 percent in 2017, and then declined to 6.42 percent in 2018. On the other hand, from 1999 to 2018, Indonesia's economic growth saw an upward trend. The trends for investment and labor force over the period were rising despite some variations. In the period 2011-2018, however, the investment trend decreased.

Although some research has investigated the effects of investment and or labor in many countries and Indonesia, including in some Indonesian provinces, no single study has explored these effects in the context of Southeast Sulawesi Province. Therefore, this study aimed to determine whether investment and labor have an effect on economic growth in Southeast Sulawesi Province. We examined this effect on an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and an error correction model (ECM-ARDL). It is hoped that the findings of this research can be used as input for the Southeast Sulawesi Province's regional government in formulating policies to encourage regional economic growth.

Literature Review

In general, an increase in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) can be achieved through an increase of physical capital or human resources due to an increase in capital stock which results in an increase in expenditures and a growth in the workforce. Either the GDP or the GRDB in a region can hardly grow and develop without an affecting stimulus factor. The GRDP growth rate is one of the measures of economic growth in a region. An economy is also said to experience growth if the volume of production of goods and services accrues.

The importance of investment in the development of economic growth is underlined by Harrod and Domar in Sukirno (2006). In their theory, Harrod and Domar (2006) regard investment as expenditure to increase an economy's capacity to make goods or as expenditure to increase the effective demand of society as a whole. Their theory points to the fact that if a capital build-in happens at a certain stage, in the next cycle the economy will be able to manufacture goods more effectively and this will eventually drive economic growth.

According to growth theories, the pace of economic growth is mainly determined by population growth, investment development, and technological advancement. Of these three factors, population growth is not necessarily seen as having a positive contribution to economic development. Pertaining to this, classical theories suggest that the uncontrolled growth of a population would cause society to regress to a deficient development level. Even so, population growth is considered to have a positive contribution to development mainly for three reasons. First, it expands the market. Second, the skilled and qualified population may give rise to various positive impacts on development. Lastly, the population may provide innovative entrepreneurs who will be a pivotal element in capital formation.

Other determinants of development, namely the formation of capital and technological improvements, will constantly make a positive contribution to economic development. Technological improvements are carried out by holding capital formation. These two determinant factors are inextricably connected. Based on the essence of the relationship between these two variables, it can be said that what is ideal for economic development is capital formation, which aims to make improvements in technology. This is in accordance with a study by Aprilia and Harianti (2014), which found that the economic growth in Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand, the Philippines, and Vietnam was significantly influenced by foreign investment and the inflation rate.

Empirical evidence demonstrates that labor conditions in developed and developing countries vary both in terms of quality and quantity. Developing countries are confronted with the fact that their labor force productivity is low. This is due to the fact that the workforce's quality remains poor. Meanwhile, in developed countries, education can become a human capital investment. As a result, the workforce's quality is high, so that the workforce's productivity is also high.

There are two fundamental approaches to human capital theory: the Nelson-Phelps approach (1966) and the Lucas approach (1988). The approach by Nelson-Phelps, Aghion, and Howitt (1966) concluded that human capital is a critical factor in generating economic growth in a country. The disparity in growth rates between countries is attributed primarily to disparities in human capital stocks. Aghion and Howitt support the Nelson-Phelps approach to the stock of human capital, which stated that, a more skilled and educated population would be more able to meet specific employment qualifications. In other words, workers with a higher level of education are more capable of responding to innovations, which will lead to an increase in the economic growth of a country (Meir & Rauch, 2000). Another approach of Lucas (1988) stresses the importance of human capital accumulation to economic development. He believes that two factors contribute to the development of the human capital of a country. These two aspects are education and learning by doing.

In his study, Barro (1998) explored the effects of education on economic growth in 100 countries during 1960-1995. The independent variables of this study included government consumption/GDP, years of schooling (as a proxy of human capital), life expectancy, inflation rate, rule of law index, democracy index, fertility rate, investment/GDP, and the growth rate of terms of trade. For the dependent variable was the growth of GDP per capita. Using a multi-linear regression analysis model, this study concluded that education has a significant impact on economic growth. In particular, the variable of human capital is more critical than the variable of physical capital (Balaceanu & Aposto, 2014).

Data and Methodology

The present study used time series data on investment (NV), the labor force (MP), and gross regional domestic product (DP) of Southeast Sulawesi Province. Data were a time series for each year from 1999 to 2018. Time-series for DP represented a proxy for economic growth. The data were sourced from the Central Statistics Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province, Indonesia.

To examine the long run effects of investment and labor on Indonesia's economic growth, we employed a cointegration model which is specified as follows

$$GDP_t = C + \alpha INV_t + \beta EMP_t + u_t \quad (1)$$

where $GDP_t = \ln DP_t$, $INV_t = \ln NV_t$ and $EMP_t = \ln MP_t$. In equation (1), C , α and β are the parameters of the regression equation. Each of these parameters is also called the long-run multiplier of investment and labor on economic growth. The notation u_t in equation (1) states the error or residual that is normally distributed and independent, as well as homoscedastic. The parameters of C , α and β are stable (Pesaran et al., 1999).

To estimate the parameters of equation (1) using the least-squares method, a cointegration model of an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bound approach was applied (Pesaran et al., 2001; Murthy & Okunade, 2016), which are specified as follows.

$$D(GDP_t) = C_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \theta_i D(GDP_{(t-i)}) + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} (\alpha_j D(INV_{(t-j)})) + \sum_{k=0}^{r-1} \beta_j D(EMP_{(t-k)}) + \delta_1 GDP_{t-1} + \delta_2 INV_{t-1} + \delta_3 EMP_{t-1} + u_t \quad (3)$$

where C_0 , θ_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, p-1$), α_j ($j = 0, 1, \dots, q-1$), β_k ($k = 0, 1, \dots, r-1$), γ_k ($k = 0, 1, \dots, q_2$) and δ_l ($l = 0, 1, 3$). The parameter C_0 is the constant parameter and the notation $D(GDP_t)$ states the GDP variable at first difference with $D(GDP_t) = GDP_t - GDP_{t-1} = GDP - GDP(-1)$. The variables in equations (1) and (3) must be stationary at I (0), or I (1) or both, and none is stationary at second difference I (2) (Pesaran et al., 1999; Sam et al., 2019).

Thus, before checking the cointegration relationship between investment, labor, and economic growth, in the first place, we tested the stationarity of all variables to ensure that none of these variables are stationary in at second difference I (2). We used two kinds of stationarity tests: the augmented Dickey-Fuller test or ADF for short (Dickey & Fuller, 1979) and the Phillips-Perron test abbreviated as PP (Phillips & Perron, 1988). The hypothesis of both tests was H_0 : time series is non-stationary, as opposed to H_1 : time series is stationary. The test criterion was to accept hypothesis H_1 : if the p-value of the test statistic is less than the significance level of 1%, 5%, or 10%.

To test for the cointegration relationship between investment, labor, and economic growth using equation (3), the hypothesis used was $H_0: \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \delta_3 = 0$ against the alternative hypothesis $H_1: \delta_1 \neq \delta_2 \neq \delta_3 \neq 0$. The alternative hypothesis states that there is a cointegration relationship between investment, labor, and economic growth. To test this hypothesis, we used the F-statistic. The criterion for acceptance of the hypothesis was determined by comparing the test statistical value with the upper bound critical value. If the test statistic's value is greater than the critical value of the upper bound I(1), then the hypothesis is accepted, indicating that a long-run cointegration relationship exists between investment, labor, and economic growth. In the next step, we estimated the long-run parameters of equation (1).

Furthermore, in this study, we also examined the short run effects of investment and labor on economic growth. For this purpose, we employed an error correction model (ECM-ARDL) specified with the following equation

$$D(GDP_t) = C_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \theta_i D(GDP_{(t-i)}) + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} (\alpha_j D(INV_{(t-j)})) + \sum_{k=0}^{r-1} \beta_j D(EMP_{(t-k)}) + \pi EC_{t-1} + u_t \quad (4)$$

In equation (4), π is the error correction parameter which states that the economic growth is corrected by $\pi\%$, indicating its long-run equilibrium, while EC_{t-1} is the error correction variable.

Drawing conclusions from testing the long run and short run effects of investment and labor on economic growth in South East Sulawesi must also be supported by fulfilling model assumptions. Thus, we checked autocorrelation, homoscedasticity and residual normality as well as the stability assumptions of the parameters of regression equation. In so doing, we used the following tests: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM, Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey, and Jarque Bera. Meanwhile, to test the stability of the parameters, we used the CUSUM test and the CUSUM Square test.

Results and Discussion

Results

In the first place, to ensure that none of the variables involved in models (1) and (3) are stationary at second difference I (2), we tested the assumption of variables stationarity. The stationary test results using the

ADF test and the PP test are summarized in Table 1. As shown in Table 1, the variables of investment and labor are stationary at first difference. Meanwhile, the variable of economic growth is stationary at the first level and difference.

Table 1: Unit Root Test

Variable	ADF Test Statistics		PP Test Statistics	
	Constant	Constant and Linear Trend	Constant	Constant and Linear Trend
INV	-0.295260	-1.938479	-0.301163	-1.890275
D(INV)	-4.697464*	-2.247319	-4.670929*	-4.827793*
EMP	-4.625360*	-3.722540**	-2.407092	-2.563461
D(EMP)	-6.691115*	-7.135124*	-6.757363*	-7.135124*
GDP	-2.313334	-1.977022	-4.505715*	-3.823093**
D(GDP)	-2.637953	-3.080490	-5.221940*	-7.186087*

Note: *, ** means significant at the 1%, 5% significance level.

In the second place, we tested for the cointegration between investment, labor, and economic growth. We obtained a test statistic value of 9.41 as a result of the F-statistic measurement. After comparing this value to the critical value of upper bound I (1) of 5.30 at a significance level of 1%, we concluded that a longrun cointegration relationship exists between investment, labor, and economic growth.

Finally, we analyzed the long run and short run effects of investment and labor on economic growth. The estimation results of the longrun parameters in equation (1) and the short run parameters in equation (3) are summarized in Table 2. In this estimation, the constant parameter is not included for it is insignificant.

Table 3: Estimation of long run and short run coefficients

Constant and independent variables	Coefficient	t-Statistic	P-value
Panel A: Long-run coefficient. Dependent variable : D(GDP)			
INV	-0.607467	-3.419673	0.0141
EMP	0.971286	6.674693	0.0005
Panel B: Short-run coefficient. Dependent variable : D(GDP)			
D(GDP(-1))	0.778885	4.990622	0.0025
D(INV)	-0.687046	-2.039310	0.0875
D(INV(-1))	-0.431061	-1.371763	0.2192
D(INV(-2))	1.515349	3.900136	0.0080
D(LINV(-3))	1.373601	4.331016	0.0049
D(EMP)	-2.048763	-3.644895	0.0108
D(EMP(-1))	-2.321950	-4.750821	0.0032
EC(-1)	-0.915510	-6.136220	0.0009

Note: *, ** are significant at 1%, 5%

Panel 2 of Table 3 above displays the estimation results of the longrun parameters. While the coefficient of investment (INV) is significant at 5 percent significance level, the labor coefficient is significant at 1 percent significance level. Thus, in the long run, investment and labor have a significant impact on southeast Sulawesi's economic development.

As for the short run parameters, the results of their estimation are shown in Panel B of the same table. All the coefficients of investment and labor are significant at both the level and the difference, except for the difference of variable D (INV (-1)), which is not significant. These results indicate that there is an effect of investment and labor on economic growth in Southeast Sulawesi in the short run.

The conclusion above must be supported by satisfying the classical assumption of equation (1) residuals and its parameters' stability. The probability values for the F-statistic of the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM autocorrelation test and the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey homoscedasticity test were 0.3078 and 0.9509, respectively. This means that the residuals of equation (1) are homoscedastic and independent (do not have autocorrelation). As for the probability of the Jarque Bera test, it is 0.496 or greater than 5%. Thus, the residuals of the regression equation are normally distributed. Furthermore, based on the stability test of the parameters using the CUSUM test and the CUSUM Square test, we concluded that the parameters of the regression equation are all stable. We can see in Figure 1 that the curved trend of the change in parameters lies between the two 5% significance limits.

Figure 1. Results of CUSUM test and CUSUM Square test

Discussion

The data analysis results using the autoregressive distribution lag (ARDL) model and the error model (ECM-ARDL) revealed that both investment and labor have a long-term and a short-term impact on economic growth, implying that any additional investment and labor will increase economic growth. This finding gives evidence to substantiate Harrod Domar's theory in Sukirno, (2006), which stresses the role of investment in boosting economic growth (capital formation). It also supports the theory of human capital put forward by Nelson-Phelps, Aghion and Howit (1966), stating that human capital is vital for the economic development of a nation.

Not only is it in line with the theory proposed by Harrod and Domar as described above, but the finding presented in this study is also in agreement with the results of the research by Athukolara (2003) and Lipsey (2000), which found that investments have a positive impact on economic growth. It, however, conflicts with that of Rafiyat et al. (2018), which reported that investments do not affect economic growth.

This present study is limited since only two variables affecting economic growth are discussed: investments and labor. In fact, different theories and findings of research have indicated a number of factors influencing economic growth, including inflation, the perceived corruption index, government spending, etc. In this regard, the researchers suggest adding several variables affecting economic growth to the future researchers.

Given the important role that investment and labor play in creating economic growth in Southeast Sulawesi, it is recommended that the Southeast Sulawesi Provincial Government adopt a number of policies as follows:

- 1.) Establishing a favorable investment climate in South East Sulawesi
- 2.) Simplify business license services procedures
- 3.) Maintain security and public order in a sustainable manner.
- 4.) Increasing workforce participation in various sectors of the economy by expanding job opportunities.
- 5.) Increase the knowledge and skills of the workforce through education and training.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Economic growth constitutes a significant macroeconomic indicator to measure the economic performance of both the state economy and the regional economy. It indicates the degree to which economic activities can generate additional income to improve the wellbeing of society over a long-term period. Many variables, including investment, labor, oil prices, energy use, and exchange rate may have an effect upon economic growth. Inflation, the perception of corruption and government expenditure also impact on economic growth. The first two mentioned variables: investment and labor, are focused in this study. This present study is particularly aimed at analyzing their effects on economic growth in South East Sulawesi Province.

In this analysis, annual time series data for the South East of Sulawesi Province from 1999 to 2018 are used for investment, labor and economic growth variables. We employ the ARDL and the ECM-ARDL model to examine these data. The analysis reveals that investments and labor significantly affect economic growth in the long and short term. On the basis of the analysis, we make some recommendations. First, an investment climate conducive to promoting investment needs to be established in South East Sulawesi. Second, procedures must be streamlined for business licensing services. Third, security and public order should be sustained. Fourth, the level of participation of workers in different areas of the economy must be increased by rising employment. Lastly, the knowledge and skills of the workforce should be enhanced through education and training.

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